

Deliverable D3.1

Report on credit and software management plan implementation

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable reports the outcomes of ELIXIR-STEERS activities focused on the design and implementation of mechanisms supporting both the recognition of research software and workflows as key research outputs and their systematic integration through Software Management Plans (SMPs). This report addresses two interconnected challenges: the need to appropriately recognise contributions that extend beyond traditional publications, and to ensure that research software development and reuse are systematically planned and documented from the early stages of research projects.

Achieving these challenges, the project, now nearly 1.5 years into its implementation (month 18), conducted a set of coordinated activities within Work Package (WP) 3, in close alignment with WP2 and WP5. These activities included scoping work, internal planning sessions, architectural design, targeted technical development, and stakeholder consultations. The result was the introduction of an architecture to support the implementation of inclusive research credit systems and the co-design of a knowledge model for SMPs which integrates credit-relevant metadata. Emphasis was placed on describing prototype implementations leveraging existing infrastructures (with a focus on those related to the ELIXIR ecosystem) while ensuring interoperability and responsiveness to practical requirements across ELIXIR Nodes. This report builds on Milestones (M) 3.1 and 3.2, which established strategic foundations and implemented a first version of the SMP interface within Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW).

Last, this report is also informed by best practices and indicators from WP2 related to sustainable and reusable software, integrated into both credit and SMP components. Collaboration with WP5 has ensured that outreach, training and communication activities support broader uptake and awareness.

In conclusion, the report provides both the rationale and technical implementation pathways for embedding credit mechanisms into the research software lifecycle. It reflects ELIXIR-STEERS' commitment to reform research assessment, supporting Open Science, and reinforcing the sustainability and visibility of software contributions across Life Sciences.

2. Contribution toward project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

Objective no. / Key Result no. Description	Contributed to:
Objective 1: Partner with user communities to create a toolkit for robust, reproducible, and green software and workflows that allow life-scientists to benefit from open science practices in the emerging European federated data landscape. (WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5)	
Key Result 1.1: Established partnerships with user communities that capture experiences and embed these in good practices for robust, reproducible, and green software and workflows (WP2)	No
Key Result 1.2: A toolkit developed consisting of guidelines, best practices and services that supports software development and recognition of individuals involved in software development (WP2, WP3)	Yes
Key Result 1.3: Community-wide agreement on key indicators for technical, scientific, and environmental benchmarking (WP2) embedded into established software and workflow benchmarking systems (WP3)	No
Key Result 1.4: Practices for robust, reproducible, and green software and workflows (WP2, WP3) are adopted and embedded in ELIXIR Nodes (WP4), supporting the European federated data landscape and Horizon Europe projects	No
Key Result 1.5: Demonstration of the greening potential and reduced carbon footprint of software best practice by applying toolkit and indicators in community-driven activities (WP2)	No
Key Result 1.6: Stimulate engagement and uptake by users via European and national communication and outreach programmes (WP5)	No
Objective 2: Enable the landscape for cross-border data analysis in the life sciences by embedding common practice across the whole European Research Area via effective national ELIXIR Nodes. (WP4, WP5)	
Key Result 2.1: Build a common toolkit to enhance the operational and managerial capacity of ELIXIR Nodes that comprise all aspects of sustainability (operational excellence, business planning, interactions with industry and impact assessment) (WP4, WP5)	No
Key Result 2.2: Expand the ELIXIR's Membership by transitioning candidate countries into fully operational national Nodes using capacity building actions (WP4, WP5)	No

<p>Key Result 2.3: Strengthen excellence in RI management with an ELIXIR training programme that complements established Europe-wide offerings with the infrastructure specific needs (WP4)</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Key Result 2.4: Strengthen the capacity of national training programmes (WP4) to scale the dissemination, training, and uptake of the ELIXIR software development toolkit for robust, reproducible, and green software and workflows (WP5)</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Key Result 2.5: Work with funders to embed the practice in data and software management plans in guidelines to grantees (WP5)</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Objective 3: Partner in Europe and internationally for global competitiveness and sustainability. (WP5)</p>	
<p>Key Result 3.1: Development of national SME and industry partnerships to support the European innovation ecosystem (WP5)</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Key Result 3.2: Partnerships with other ESFRI RIs to strengthen the wider RI landscape (WP5) and support adoption of robust, reproducible, and green workflows across RI facilities.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Key Result 3.3: Foster global knowledge-exchange to drive good international practices and embed international partnerships in Node activities (WP5)</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Key Result 3.4: Deliver a Node dissemination and communications toolkit that enables ELIXIR Nodes to amplify engagement with scientists and other stakeholders (WP5)</p>	<p>No</p>

3. Introduction

In the last decades, Life Sciences research activities have become increasingly diverse, going beyond the publication of research articles. Tasks such as data curation, standardisation, resource annotation, software development, and workflow automation now form an integral part of research routines and methodologies across disciplines. However, despite the growing effort invested by scientists in such tasks, the respective contributions are often overlooked, insufficiently documented, or undervalued in the context of research assessment, whether at the level of individual researchers, research teams or even entire organisations.

In the case of research software and their accompanying workflows, this insufficient acknowledgement, documentation, and recognition of these contributions not only undermines the work of researchers and organisations that offer essential contributions to the research community at large but also hinders the long-term reuse and sustainability of research software. To address these gaps, there is a growing need for improved frameworks that formally acknowledge and credit software development, maintenance, and management as a core research output. In parallel, better documentation practices, similar to those already implemented through data management plans, should be adopted to capture technical details, dependencies, and development processes to support software reuse, enhance reproducibility, and foster a more inclusive and accurate representation of research contributions.

This report aims to provide technical insights into the implementation of framework reforms within the research ecosystem, alongside other actions that can pave the way for a more inclusive crediting system and improve the reuse and documentation of research software through the use of research Software Management Plans (SMPs), which are (living) documents outlining how research software is developed, maintained, shared, and preserved throughout and/or after a research project. It is grounded in the recognition that valuable research assets, to which researchers dedicate significant effort and which are essential to the research process broadly, go beyond publications. The main focus of the report is on research software and workflows, which are fundamental outputs of Life Sciences' research and should be considered first-class citizens within the landscape of research assessment.

To summarise, the scope includes two interlinked pillars,

1. enabling mechanisms to assign credit to researchers for research assets beyond publications with an emphasis on research software and workflows, and
2. ensuring that these research software and workflows are systematically considered from the onset of research projects via inclusion in SMPs.

To ensure the effective design and implementation of research software crediting and documentation mechanisms, we undertook a series of activities focused on how contributions to research software and workflows can be better captured, assessed, and recognised, including community consultations. A key part of this effort involved aligning SMPs with crediting practices for researchers to reflect not just how software is developed and maintained, but also who contributed and in what role.

In addition to regular internal Work Package (WP) meetings focused on objectives and specific tasks, feedback-driven sessions were held with technical stakeholders and community members to refine the design of both the SMP knowledge model and the integration of credit-relevant metadata (details

on the specific activities follow in the next sections). This participatory process helped ensure that tools and templates developed under ELIXIR-STEERS are grounded in real-world needs and are interoperable with platforms relevant to the implementation of inclusive crediting mechanisms (such as those presented in Section 5.1.1). Embedding features that facilitate credit into SMPs is essential to support visibility, sustainability, and recognition of software and workflows as a research output.

This report summarises the aforementioned activities and their main results and builds upon the work that was undertaken in the context of [Milestone 3.1](#) (“Strategy for inclusion of credit for research assets decided”) and [Milestone 3.2](#) (“First version of Software Management Plan interface implemented in Data Stewardship Wizard”). Additionally, it is directly informed by the outputs of WP2, in particular of T2.1 (“Building the technical toolkit for software best-practices”) and T2.2 (“Identifying efficiency indicators for research software and workflows”), which define the best practices and indicators for high-quality, sustainable, and reusable research software and workflows. Within WP3, the target is to ensure that these practices are acknowledged and that (at least some of) the indicators are operationalised, integrating and demonstrating them into credit and SMP platforms. There is also synergy with WP5 (“Communications, outreach, industry and international”), which focuses on community outreach, training, and dissemination. The implementation and promotion of software management plans and credit mechanisms in WP3 are closely tied to awareness-raising and capacity-building activities in WP5. Furthermore, WP3 as a whole, contributes to the long-term vision of ELIXIR-STEERS, ensuring that these features support operational needs of ELIXIR Nodes (WP4) and are aligned with broader European efforts in research assessment reform and Open Science.

4. Description of work accomplished

In this section, we present the activities that were planned and carried out in relation to this deliverable. We first address the main activities related to the implementation of an inclusive credit framework (Section 4.1) and SMPs (Section 4.2). Then, we elaborate on work interlinked to other ELIXIR-STEERS work packages (Section 4.3) and other relevant initiatives (Section 4.4).

4.1 Activities Focused on Credit

During the initial months, WP3 activities related to research software credit focused on developing a plan to enable and support the recognition of research assets beyond publications. This effort concluded in the ELIXIR STEERS milestone report titled [“M3.1 - Strategy for Inclusion of Credit for Research Assets Decided”](#), which was published in October 2024. The report proposed a strategy to credit scientists for diverse research contributions and artefacts beyond traditional publications, including research software, data, training materials. Central to the proposed strategy is an ecosystem leveraging existing platforms. [APICURON](#) - originally designed to credit and acknowledge contributions from biocurators - acts as an aggregator and contribution tracker that can be expanded to broader research assets. [BIP! Scholar](#) enables researchers to build enriched academic profiles highlighting a wide range of activities, using data from scholarly graphs (like the [OpenAIRE Graph](#)) and [ORCID](#). Together, these platforms, along with other open infrastructure (see Section 5.1.1), can support inclusive recognition and visibility for researchers across various outputs.

Following the publication of the aforementioned report, ELIXIR-STEERS credit experts focused on refining and extending the proposed ecosystem and its components and providing more detailed implementation guidance related to relevant challenges and opportunities identified (see Section 5.1.3). This work also took into account, and in some cases contributed to, parallel efforts from other

initiatives, such as [Deliverable Report D5.1](#) of the EVERSE project and the conceptual architecture proposed by the [O14RRA](#) Working Group (WG) of [CoARA](#). The outcomes of this extended effort are detailed in Section 5 of this report. Moreover, detailed information on joint activities with the aforementioned external initiatives is provided in Section 4.4.

In parallel, ELIXIR-STEERS experts are currently working on the development of a Policy Brief focused on providing recommendations on how to systematically credit researchers for contributions beyond traditional scholarly publications (e.g., software, tools, workflows, data, and training materials) in the Life Sciences.

Finally, it is worth noting that a collaborative meeting between the task leaders of Task 3.1 (“Enable crediting scientists for research assets”) and Task 3.2 (“Contributing towards sustainable research software through Software Management Plans”) was held on 13/01/2025, aimed at identifying areas of shared interest. The outcomes of this exchange (together with the outputs of some feedback-driven meetings organised by Task 3.2) enabled SMP experts to incorporate requirements from credit platforms (see Sections 4.2 and 5.2) into their design considerations. Moreover, the discussion led to the identification of potential synergies (mostly targeting the needs for common standards), allowing both pillars to align on key issues such as proper software citation techniques, the use of persistent identifiers, and the adoption of standardized contribution roles. First results towards this direction are discussed in Section 5.3.

4.2 Activities Focused on SMPs

In the initial phase, work under [Milestone 3.2](#), ‘First Version of Software Management Plan Interface Implemented in Data Stewardship Wizard’ (submitted in January 2025), focused on designing the initial SMP interface and integrating it into the Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW). Building on this foundation, ELIXIR-STEERS continued to refine and expand the SMP Knowledge Model within DSW. The initial implementation provided a structured, standards-aligned model to support the planning and documentation of research software projects. It included foundational features for crediting contributors, referencing persistent identifiers (PIDs), and describing roles and licences. This served as a robust starting point for further enhancement in collaboration with the ELIXIR community.

To improve crediting functionality and ensure alignment with real-world needs and integration requirements, a series of meetings and feedback loops were conducted. These focused both on technical adjustments and on practical use cases across ELIXIR Nodes and platforms:

- **13 February 2025 – Online demonstration and feedback session**

This session introduced the first version of the SMP Knowledge Model and its implementation in DSW. Participants were guided through its use and shown how to provide structured feedback using a shared commenting document. The session aimed to lower the barrier for community input by demonstrating the interactive nature of SMP completion and highlighting how responses could be mapped to outputs.

- **1 April 2025 – Focused online workshop on SMPs and crediting**

A detailed walkthrough of the SMP Knowledge Model was conducted with selected stakeholders, including members of the Tools Platform and data stewardship experts. Discussions focused on how to improve or extend the model to better capture contributor roles, contact details, licensing information, and connections to external identifiers such as

ORCID iDs. Particular attention was given to aligning SMP fields with services like [bio.tools](#), [APICURON](#), and [OpenEBench](#), ensuring the captured metadata could support future interoperability.

- **5 June 2025 – ELIXIR All Hands feedback F2F workshop**

Held during the annual ELIXIR All Hands Meeting, this session invited feedback across all chapters of the SMP Knowledge Model. Participants, many of whom had experience in research software development, provided insights on credit-related sections, including documentation of responsibilities, contributor types, and long-term software sustainability practices. This input helped validate earlier proposals and highlighted new areas for refinement.

In parallel to these structured meetings, **feedback was iteratively collected and integrated into the knowledge model and templates**. Suggestions from users were regularly reviewed and applied to refine question text, expand guidance, introduce additional options (e.g. contributor roles), and improve usability. These changes were synchronised with updates to the **human-readable and machine-actionable** document templates, ensuring consistency across all SMP outputs.

This iterative development process reflects the **living document nature of SMPs** and the need for flexibility in accommodating evolving community expectations. It also ensured that technical improvements directly supported the goal of transparent, structured crediting within and beyond ELIXIR. Further details on alignment with external services and systems are presented in section 4.5.

4.3 Work Accomplished Interlinked with other WPs on Credit and SMPs

Work in WP3 on building an ecosystem for crediting and recognition of research artefacts beyond publications is tightly connected with the work carried out by WP2, specifically as part of Task 2.1 Building the technical toolkit for software best-practices (Lead beneficiary: UNIPD) and Task 2.2 Identifying efficiency indicators for research software and workflows (Lead beneficiary: CERTH).

In the context of the work of WP2 Task 2.1, existing platforms - [APICURON](#), [ORCID](#), [BIP! Scholar](#), [WorkflowHub](#), [bio.tools](#) and [OpenEBench](#) - are leveraged to enable proper attribution of research contributions for software, workflows, data and training materials. This approach, relying on the use of persistent identifiers (PIDs) and enriched metadata, enables consistent recognition of a diverse range of research artefacts while promoting Open Science and aligning with FAIR and sustainability principles. At the same time, the involvement of WorkflowHub and OpenEBench plays a key role in supporting the acknowledgment of the effort given by researchers and engineers to improve reproducibility and optimisation of their scientific workflows, by capturing relevant metadata (e.g., datasets used, benchmarking information).

Moreover, WP3 interacts with WP2 Task 2.2 by providing a list of relevant infrastructure components (see document [Flashcards of resources](#)) and indicators to support the evaluation of efficiency, quality, impact and recognition of research software and workflows. In this context, OpenEBench provides benchmarking capabilities to assess software performance and workflow reproducibility while APICURON and BIP! Scholar aggregate metadata related to research contributions.

As part of the collaborative work in WP3, Task 3.3 has contributed to the credit and sustainability objectives of WP3 advancing the technical benchmarking of workflows in Life Science. More

specifically, a new software was developed, [Execution Metrics Collector](#), to capture low-level process metrics and derive high-level indicators, including computational efficiency and carbon footprint estimations ([ELIXIR-STEERS T3.3 Technical metrics](#)). This work, carried out in collaboration with WP2 and several ELIXIR Communities (e.g. Single Cell, Microbiome, Proteomics), enables the assessment of workflow performance and reproducibility. The identified benchmarking strategies and use cases, documented in Milestone 3.3, “Use cases for benchmarking workflows identified” [report](#) (submitted in April 2025), directly support crediting practices, generating indicators of quality and sustainability that can be integrated into SMPs and credit frameworks.

4.4 Work Accomplished Interlinked with other Initiatives on Credit and SMPs

ELIXIR-STEERS experts actively considered the work of relevant external initiatives and, where possible, contributed to their activities and outputs. The following paragraphs provide a detailed account of these collaborative efforts.

Regarding the implementation of an inclusive and fair research credit system, ELIXIR-STEERS experts actively considered the work of relevant international and European initiatives, particularly the CoARA working groups and EOSC expert groups. In several cases, ELIXIR-STEERS experts were not only participants but also played leading roles in shaping the discussions within these groups:

- **CoARA's WG Towards Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment (OI4RRA):** OI4RRA is a CoARA Working Group dedicated to supporting institutions in transitioning from proprietary research infrastructures and information systems to open, interoperable alternatives enabling the adoption of responsible research assessment practices. ELIXIR-STEERS experts are participating in the activities of this WG with the emphasis given on the work of a subgroup that had the aim to suggest a conceptual architecture for the implementation of a responsible research assessment framework that is built on open infrastructures. The respective [report](#) was published in April 2024 with active contributions from ELIXIR-STEERS experts. It also naturally influenced part of the work performed in the context of the current deliverable. Indicatively all components of the architecture described in Section 5.1.1, were mapped in at least one of the four tiers of OI4RRA's conceptual architecture. Finally, ELIXIR-STEERS experts were also involved in the creation of a [policy brief](#) on the transition from closed proprietary systems to open infrastructures for responsible research assessment and a [report](#) on the principles of Open Infrastructures for responsible research assessment.
- **EOSC Expert Group on Opportunity Area 5 (OA5) - Integrate Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition, and Upskilling:** This group, works among other causes (training, learning paths and engagement), on supporting EOSC-A and relevant EOSC projects to reach CoARA objectives ([ARRA's 10 commitments](#)), which among main systemic change objectives, involve research and researchers crediting commitments, for example, recognising diverse research contributions, prioritising qualitative evaluation over narrow metrics, abandoning inappropriate use of indicators like JIF and h-index, and refining assessment criteria and tools are key steps toward ensuring fair and meaningful credit in research. Further, the group is committed to work towards a quality assurance framework and certification mechanisms for trainers and trainees. After all, training is key and should be universal.
- **EOSC Expert Group on Opportunity Area 7 (OA7) - Research software:** The OA7 Expert Group is dedicated to addressing the key challenges and opportunities related to research software within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) framework. Given that it is broadly

acknowledged that software plays a fundamental role in research, not only as a tool, but also as a valuable research output and object of study. This group focuses specifically on software developed for research purposes or produced during the research process, recognising its importance in enabling scientific discovery across disciplines. To support the quality, sustainability, and long-term preservation of such software, the OA7 group is working to promote best practices and services that meet the diverse needs of those who develop it, from researchers who code occasionally, to dedicated Research Software Engineers (RSEs). Central to this effort is the need to ensure that both software and its developers receive appropriate credit and recognition, as this is essential for fostering sustainable development practices and encouraging wider adoption. ELIXIR-STEERS credit experts are involved to ensure alignment regarding the respective tasks.

Moreover, the project activities related to both the research credit mechanisms and the SMPs within ELIXIR-STEERS has been strongly informed by, and aligned with, other European projects to improve research assessment and support FAIR, open research outputs. Indicatively, the activities of the following projects are highly relevant to ELIXIR-STEERS:

- **EVERSE** (<https://everse.software/>): The EVERSE project aims to create a framework for research software and code excellence, collaboratively designed and championed by the research communities. The objective is to establish a European network focused on Research Software Quality and to lay the foundations for a future Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence. Among others, EVERSE provides structured approaches for evaluating and crediting research software and its [D5.1 report](#) offers an overview of European initiatives on credit, metadata standards, and evaluation models. Furthermore, the development of [RSQkit](#), a knowledge base designed around a framework for research software excellence, which aims to incorporate aspects involving community curation, quality assessment, and best practices for research software, was particularly relevant. It includes guidance on citation practices and contributor roles, which informed enhancements to the SMP Knowledge Model in ELIXIR-STEERS, particularly in areas related to licensing, identifiers (e.g. ORCID), and structured contributor information.
- **GraspOS** (<https://graspos.eu/>): The GraspOS project is an EOSC-related project funded by the European Commission with the aim to develop, assess and put into operation an (EOSC integrated) open federated infrastructure to support and enable policy reforms towards “Open-Science-aware” Responsible Research Assessment. Among others, the GraspOS infrastructure offers open resources to enable recognition of diverse outputs contributing to the ELIXIR-STEERS activities related to the inclusive research crediting system. Furthermore, its focus on persistent identifiers, machine-actionable metadata, and transparent attribution complements our technical strategy for SMP integration. The enhancements made to the SMP Knowledge Model—including those related to author information, contributor roles, and reuse—are compatible with the metadata exposure practices discussed in GraspOS.
- **OStrails** (<https://ostrails.eu/>): OStrails aims to Streamline FAIRness, interconnectivity and machine actionability across Planning, Tracking and Assessing research phases. The work on planning focuses on Data Management Plan (DMP) tools and practices, emphasizing the need for standardization, interoperability, and extension to cover essential research outputs such as software. In this context, OStrails activities are highly relevant and complementary to the SMP initiatives within ELIXIR-STEERS.

Furthermore, there are various other projects that have produced or are producing outputs of relevance to the ELIXIR-STEERS activities. Projects like [OPUS](#), [Skills4EOSC](#), and [CoARA Boost](#) with contributions in the fields of research credit and assessment and researchers career development; projects such as [FAIR-IMPACT](#), [FAIRCORE4EOSC](#), and [SciLake](#) that contribute to FAIR practices and scientific knowledge standardisation; as well as previous ELIXIR-focused projects, like [ELIXIR-CONVERGE](#), which laid the foundational groundwork upon which ELIXIR-STEERS builds. It is also worth mentioning that relevant activities are included in the current work programmes of various ELIXIR platforms (e.g., the Data Platform work programme includes tasks related to research credit and recognition beyond traditional publications).

Finally, as part of Milestone 3.2, we conducted an extensive review of existing SMP-related resources from across ELIXIR and external communities. This included templates, guidance documents, and checklists—many of which already contained elements relevant to crediting. While these resources were individually useful, they varied significantly in structure and terminology. A key objective in ELIXIR-STEERS was to synthesise this material into a coherent, non-redundant framework that would guide researchers clearly and effectively. Care was taken to avoid duplication, ensure consistency across chapters of the SMP, and streamline how credit-relevant information (e.g. contributor details, roles, and licences) is collected and reused.

By coordinating with these external efforts and structuring our work to support compatibility with widely adopted standards (e.g. CodeMeta, CFF, SPDX), the SMP and crediting components developed in ELIXIR-STEERS are positioned to function both within the ELIXIR ecosystem and across the broader European research infrastructure landscape.

5. Results

In this section, we present the outputs of the activities described in Section 4. In Section 5.1, we present a detailed blueprint for an architecture that can be used for the implementation of an inclusive research credit framework that takes into consideration activities and contributions related to software and other research assets that go beyond publications. Then, in Section 5.2, we outline technical matters that are important on the implementation of platforms for the creation of Software Management Plans (SMPs). Finally, in Section 5.3, we discuss cross-cutting topics which are related to the implementation of both concepts.

5.1 Architecture for the Implementation of an Inclusive Research Credit Framework

This section presents a detailed blueprint for an architecture designed to support an inclusive research credit framework that recognizes contributions to research assets beyond publications, with a particular emphasis given on research software.

5.1.1 Outline of the Architecture

The following figure presents a high-level architecture of an ecosystem that can facilitate the implementation of an inclusive research credit framework. This architecture is based on an extension of the blueprint introduced in [Milestone M3.1](#) taking also into consideration a landscape analysis performed by the [EOSC-EVERSE](#) project (“[D5.1](#) - Landscape analysis of existing rewards and mechanisms for research software and training activities”) as well as additional relevant work such as the [Conceptual Architecture for the Implementation of a Responsible Research Assessment Framework Built on Open Infrastructures](#) published by the [OI4RRA](#) working group of [CoARA](#). It is worth mentioning that the current section builds upon relevant work on EOSC-EVERSE’s D5.1 bringing in additional insights.

Figure 1: High-level architecture of an ecosystem to support the implementation of an inclusive research credit framework.

The main components of this architecture are the following:

- **Research Publishing Platforms.** These platforms are designed to collect, maintain, and publish research assets submitted by researchers (e.g., research software code) as well as information related to the respective research activities (e.g., software development and documentation). They may also assign persistent identifiers (PIDs) to these assets and gather basic metadata related to them. Indicative examples of such platforms include Research Asset Repositories (e.g., source code repositories like [GitHub](#), preprint repositories like [ArXiv](#) and general-purpose repositories like [Zenodo](#)), Research Journals & Publishers, and Research Activity Registries (e.g., [ELIXIR TeSS](#) and [OpenPlato](#) for training activities). Platforms in this category belong to the “Foundation” and/or “Publishing Venues” tiers of OI4RRA’s conceptual architecture.
- **Researcher PID Providers:** These platforms provide researchers with persistent identifiers (PIDs), which can be used during the submission of research assets to ensure their unique identification. Publishing platforms incorporate researcher PIDs in the assets’ metadata, enabling aggregators and recognition platforms to appropriately recognize a researcher’s activities and contributions. [ORCID](#) is a well-known example of a researcher PID providing platform. Platforms in this category belong to the “Foundation” tier of OI4RRA’s conceptual architecture.
- **Research Metadata Enrichment Platforms.** These platforms enrich the basic research asset metadata provided by the Research Publishing Platforms with missing annotations. The types of annotations vary according to the availability of metadata registered in the publishing platforms to be enriched and may include research performance indicators (e.g., usage counts, citation counts), contribution roles (e.g., according to the [CRediT taxonomy](#)), scientific fields/topics, and more. The enrichments could be automatically generated or curated by experts. Indicative examples of metadata enrichment platforms include [BIP! DB](#) (for citation-based indicators), [UsageCounts](#) (for usage metrics), and [OpenEBench](#) (for benchmarking information of research software). Platforms in this category are part of the “Metadata Aggregations” tier of OI4RRA’s conceptual architecture.
- **Research Metadata Aggregators.** These platforms collect, merge, de-duplicate, clean, and homogenize research-related metadata from various sources, providing end users with easy access to the aggregated information. Indicative examples of such platforms are [Crossref](#), which collects scholarly metadata from various publishers, and the [OpenAIRE Graph](#) that collects metadata from thousands of repositories and other open sources of scholarly information. In many cases, Research Metadata Aggregators are accessible for querying and processing in the form of Knowledge Graphs, often referred to as Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs). Aggregators are part of the “Metadata Aggregation” tier of OI4RRA’s conceptual architecture.
- **Researcher Contribution Trackers.** These platforms aim to track the connections between researchers and research contributions or activities. Additional context (e.g., the exact role of a researcher in an activity) may also be captured. As it is evident, this type of platform is crucial in enabling proper crediting for researchers. Indicative examples of such platforms are [ORCID](#), which collects various types of contributions by researchers (e.g., publications, datasets), and [APICURON](#), which tracks research database curation

contributions by researchers. Platforms in this category belong to the “Metadata Aggregation” tier of OI4RRA’s conceptual architecture. There is a strong connection and overlap with the Research Metadata Enrichment Platforms, however, Researcher Contribution Trackers are very central to crediting systems and this is why we selected to present them as a separate category.

- **Research Achievement Gamification Platforms.** These platforms collect research-related information from Research Metadata Aggregators and Researcher Contribution Trackers to provide gamification features, such as badges and leaderboards, to incentivise research work or good practices (e.g., Open Science practices). [APICURON](#) is a platform that offers such features to researchers for database curation activities. These platforms belong to the “Research Assessment Support Services” tier of OI4RRA’s conceptual architecture.
- **Academic Profile Platforms.** These platforms collect information from Research Metadata Aggregators and Researcher Contribution Trackers to create and make publicly available academic profiles that facilitate recognition and enable sharing and comprehension of research contributions. These platforms summarise a researcher’s contributions often offering also relevant analytics and visualizations. [ORCID](#) offers basic academic profile functionality. Another indicative example that supports various types of profile templates is [BIP! Scholar](#). These platforms belong to the “Research Assessment Support Services” tier of OI4RRA’s conceptual architecture.

The interconnections among the aforementioned components are illustrated in Figure 1. At the core of the architecture lie (a) the *Research Publishing Platforms*, which capture the basic metadata submitted by researchers when publishing research outputs of various kinds (e.g., publications, datasets, software), (b) the *Research Metadata Enrichment Platforms*, which augment this metadata with information generated post-publication (e.g., impact or usage indicators, automatically assigned topics), and (c) the *Research Contribution Trackers*, which establish links between research outputs and individual researchers leveraging the persistent identifiers provided by *Researcher PID Providers*. This wealth of information, provided by various sources (since multiple publishers, enrichers, and trackers exist), is collected, deduplicated, cleaned, and harmonized by *Research Metadata Aggregators* that make it available to everyone in a convenient form (e.g., as scientific knowledge graphs). Built on top of this aggregated metadata layer are value-added services such as *Research Achievement Gamification Platforms* and *Academic Profile Platforms* offering recognition and crediting mechanisms to researchers and other interested stakeholders. The former offer badges and leaderboards to encourage positive research culture and practices, while the latter present comprehensive CVs of individual researchers often enhanced with analytics and visualizations to highlight individual contributions and impact.

5.1.2 Metadata Standardisation & Interoperability

A credit system like the one that can be implemented by the architecture outlined in the previous section, also relies on using and properly adapting existing standards and specifications to achieve standardisation and interoperability within the respective ecosystem. More specifically:

- **Software metadata standards.** Using common metadata standards that can be used by different sources to describe in detail researcher activities related to software (or other contributions beyond publications), is very important for the implementation of a

credit system that will take into consideration this type of contributions by researchers. Established metadata standards can significantly facilitate any implementation of a relevant credit system because, ideally, such systems should attempt to be inclusive by incorporating metadata records by multiple sources.

- **Citation standards for software.** Software tools are often being cited in research publications, hence a standardized citation framework for these activities would not only ensure proper attribution but also provide insights about their usage and impact in the scientific community. Moreover, unified citation practices can enhance the discoverability and reuse of software tools, further strengthening the research ecosystem as a whole.
- **Contribution role taxonomies for software-related activities.** The existence of taxonomies for contribution roles in research software development is essential for ensuring that all contributors receive appropriate recognition for their efforts. These activities often involve diverse roles (e.g., coding, testing, and documentation). Without a clear and standardized taxonomy, the varied contributions risk being homogenized or overlooked, which can lead to inequities in credit allocation and discourage participation in these vital activities.
- **Researcher Persistent Identifiers (PIDs).** Correct and unique identification of researchers is critical to implement any credit system that recognises the activities and contributions of individual researchers.

5.1.3 Implementation: Challenges & Opportunities

The following paragraphs outline key challenges and opportunities associated with implementing the described ecosystem to support an inclusive research credit framework. We begin by examining the necessary standards, followed by a discussion of the essential platforms.

Focusing first on the necessary metadata standards to describe research software-related contributions, the RDA's Scientific Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework ([SKG-IF](#)) Working Group has been working to develop a common language for all Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), ensuring consistency in the terminology used when exposing fundamental scholarly metadata. This framework explicitly includes software as a distinct category of research products. Beyond that, other widely established standards, such as [CodeMeta](#), address similar needs. Consequently, we could conclude that there is significant process in determining common metadata standards for software, however further alignment may still be necessary to ensure greater consistency and interoperability.

Efforts to standardize software citation practices have also gained momentum recently. The [FORCE11 Software Citation Working Group](#) published in 2016 a set of principles emphasising the importance of software citation (Smith AM et al. 2016). These principles advocate for proper credit and attribution, unique identification, persistence, accessibility, and specificity in software citations. Building on these principles, in 2019, a report titled "Software Citation Implementation Challenges" (Katz D. S. et al. 2019) examined issues impacting scholarly attribution of research software, provided updated implementation guidance, and identified where best practices and solutions were still needed. Further developments came in 2021 with comprehensive software citation guidelines for journals and conference proceedings (Katz D. S. et al. 2021). In 2022, the HEP Software Foundation and the Institute for Research and Innovation for Software in High-Energy Physics organized a workshop on the topic of Software Citation and Recognition in HEP and the key

findings and recommendations were presented at the 26th International Conference on Computing in High Energy and Nuclear Physics and in a relevant report (Feickert, M. et al. 2023).

Contributions to research software can vary widely, involving diverse roles such as software architect, coder, debugger, tester, and team manager. This diversity complicates the assignment of credit and recognition to individuals involved in software development. Several initiatives are attempting to provide controlled vocabularies for the related activities including the generic Contributor Role Ontology ([CRO](#)), the more focused INRIA's Taxonomy for Software Contributions (introduced in a relevant [report](#)) and [The Software Credit Taxonomy](#). However, increased alignment seems to be needed, similarly to other standards.

Shifting the focus to the necessary platforms, there is already strong representation across most identified categories, with existing platforms well-equipped to support credit mechanisms that account for research software and training activities. First of all, this is the case for Research Publishing Platforms. Code repositories, like [GitHub](#), and other software repositories or registries, like the [WorkflowHub](#) (for scientific workflows), [bio.tools](#) (for life science software tools), and [Docker Hub](#) (for containers), are well-established and their use is a standard practice for researchers involved in research software projects. At the same time, general-purpose research asset repositories, like [Zenodo](#), support the creation of software entries minting persistent identifiers (e.g., DOIs) for them. Moreover, various journals and conferences support publishing specialized articles describing research software projects.

Furthermore, [ORCID](#) is a community standard Researcher PID provider. ORCID identifiers are widely used by researchers from various domains and are supported by scientific publishers and research funding organisations to enable the unique identification of individuals. While other researcher identifiers exist, such as ResearcherID (by Web of Science) and profile codes from platforms like Google Scholar, ORCID IDs remain the most widely adopted persistent identifiers in research, though not all researchers have one.

Regarding the research metadata enrichment, there are a variety of platforms offering diverse types of enrichments. Indicatively, the [SciNoBo](#) Fields of Science classification platform automatically assigns fields and topics to research publications, while the [BIP! Ranker](#) calculates citation-based impact indicators for research products. The Tools Observatory of the [OpenEBench](#) platform provides various indicators for research software availability and performance. These platforms typically integrate their enrichments into Research Metadata Aggregators. For instance, both SciNoBo and BIP! Ranker feed into the OpenAIRE Graph. However, such platforms often focus on publications and there is space for improvement in supporting similar enrichments for research software and training activities. Indicatively, although BIP! Ranker supports calculating citation-based impact indicators for research software tools, those indicators are based on direct citations of publications to software DOIs. However, this is expected to collect only a fraction of the software project's impact since it is very common for researchers to cite the corresponding software article or simply mention the software repository inside the manuscript (e.g., in a footnote). As a result, an extension of the platform is needed to support more comprehensive indicators for research software projects. Similar cases can be found for other enrichment platforms in the case of software-related activities.

In recent years, various organizations have provided open Research Metadata Aggregators. Among the most widely known open aggregators are [OpenAlex](#) and the [OpenAIRE Graph](#). OpenAlex focuses on publications and basic research-related entities, such as researchers,

institutions, and grants. The OpenAIRE Graph has a broader focus also covering datasets, software and other types of research products.

Regarding Researcher Contribution Trackers, [ORCID](#) is the most widely used and, it supports tracking for each researcher a wide variety of research works (publications, books, datasets, software, etc.), peer reviewing activity, research funding, and other types of contributions. Since ORCID is a general-purpose tracker, the information captured for some types of contributions is rather basic and this creates the necessity of other, more specialised tracking platforms to address the need of keeping more detailed information for them. An indicative example is [APICURON](#) that focuses on tracking database curation activities in detail supporting to push generalised entries for the same contributions to ORCID. In the context of the EOSC-EVERSE project (already mentioned previously), APICURON is planned to be extended so that it can also cover similar types of information for research software and training activities.

APICURON is also an indicative platform offering Research Achievement Gamification functionalities. More specifically, it offers leaderboard and badging functionalities encouraging greater engagement in time-consuming and routine tasks such as database record curation and (in the context of EOSC-EVERSE) research software development.

Finally, when it comes to Academic Profile Platforms, a wide range of services is already available. [ORCID](#) is a key example, though its profiles primarily serve as structured lists of contributions with basic metadata about researchers. Other platforms, such as [Google Scholar](#), provide profile functionalities but are largely centred on publications, as these are the most readily available metadata. [BIP! Scholar](#) is a platform that takes a broader approach by supporting multiple profile templates tailored to diverse researcher needs. These templates may incorporate various researcher-level indicators or support modern formats, such as narrative CVs, to provide a more comprehensive representation of academic contributions. BIP! Scholar is also set to be expanded to better accommodate academic profile templates that emphasize research software ensuring a more holistic approach to researcher recognition. The need to better incorporate profile elements that better track activities related to research software are crucial for the implementation of an inclusive credit and recognition framework.

5.2 Implementation of SMPs

The focus on crediting and its relation to SMP resulted in the second iteration of the Software Management Planning Knowledge Model. It builds on the foundation laid in Milestone 3.2, introducing several targeted enhancements that support improved contributor crediting, transparency of reuse, and better alignment with research assessment and open science practices. These changes were guided by community feedback (see Section 4.2), input from related initiatives (see Section 4.4), and the technical priorities of the ELIXIR-STEERS project. The updated version of the Knowledge Model is released as version 1.1, with corresponding updates to the document templates to ensure consistency and usability.

5.2.1 Improved Guidance and Referencing

Each section of the Knowledge Model now includes extended guidance text, helping researchers understand both the rationale behind each question and how to respond in line with good practices. Where relevant, references are provided to external sources such as RSQkit, The Turing Way, and FAIR software guidelines. These improvements particularly support questions about authorship,

attribution, and reuse, ensuring that SMP users are encouraged to credit upstream software appropriately and clearly document their own contributions.

The guidance also explains the practical value of adopting community-recognised tools such as CONTRIBUTORS files, CODEOWNERS, and CITATION.cff, which support both human-readable and machine-actionable credit structures. These concepts are referenced directly in the relevant questions, helping researchers apply them when preparing software for sharing or publication.

✓ II.1 Who are the contributors?

Include names, roles (e.g. developer, maintainer, tester), and persistent identifiers such as ORCID iDs where possible. This information supports proper credit attribution, transparency, and alignment with best practices for research software citation.

You should also consider using standard files such as CONTRIBUTORS or CODEOWNERS in your repository. For citation purposes, contributors shall also be listed in a CITATION.cff file. Following these conventions improves visibility and ensures compatibility with tools and platforms that track research outputs.

🔗 External links: [Research Software Citation: Cite and Make Citable](#), [RSQKit: Citing Software](#)

📄 Expand all 📄 Collapse all

▼ Marek Suchánek

▼ Jan Slifka

5.2.2 Alignment with CITATION.cff

In support of future automation, multiple questions across the Knowledge Model were revised or added to align with the structure of the CITATION.cff file format. This includes fields covering author names and roles, affiliations, funding details, version information, licensing, and preferred citation formats. By ensuring that these elements are captured in a structured way during the SMP creation process, it becomes feasible to automatically generate a complete CITATION.cff file as an output of the SMP. This will further encourage the consistent use of proper citation metadata across ELIXIR-hosted or ELIXIR-related software.

5.2.3 Documenting Reuse and Previous Projects

A new section was introduced to allow users to indicate previous software projects or components that the current project is building upon or extending. This is important for both provenance tracking and crediting. The model supports descriptive text as well as linking to persistent identifiers, such as DOIs or repository URLs. This change supports recognition of foundational work, encourages reuse, and enhances transparency across the software lifecycle.

5.2.4 Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for Contributors and Institutions

To ensure high-quality metadata and facilitate downstream crediting, version 1.1 of the Knowledge Model includes integration with PID services. Specifically, the SMP model supports:

- ORCID iDs for individual contributors, enabling name disambiguation and linking to researcher profiles.

✓ **II.1.a.2.a.2** **ORCID**

ORCID ensures unambiguous attribution of your contributions by linking them to a persistent researcher identifier. Including your ORCID helps improve visibility, recognition, and interoperability across systems.

External links: [Create or access your ORCID iD](#)

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✓ **II.1.a.2.a.2** **ORCID**

ORCID ensures unambiguous attribution of your contributions by linking them to a persistent researcher identifier. Including your ORCID helps improve visibility, recognition, and interoperability across systems.

External links: [Create or access your ORCID iD](#)

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Clear answer

- ROR (Research Organization Registry) IDs for institutions, allowing affiliation data to be consistently and reliably recorded. Note: ROR integration has been improved, was already present in v1.0, but now switched to newer API v2.

These identifiers are used not only for display purposes but also to support structured exports and future interoperability with platforms such as OpenAIRE, APICURON, BIP! Scholar, and research software directories.

The Knowledge Model integrates these PID services directly within the DSW interface using the ORCID and ROR APIs, providing lookup and autocomplete functionality for ease of use. This helps ensure data accuracy and reduces entry errors while enabling enhanced discoverability and attribution.

5.2.5 Extended Coverage of Licensing, Funding, and IPR

Several new questions and refinements were introduced to enhance the documentation of licensing, funding sources, and intellectual property (IPR). These include:

- Start and end dates of software licences, where applicable, particularly for time-limited or conditional licences.
- The ability to list one or more funding projects or grants under which the software is being developed, with support for linking to project PIDs or grant references.
- IPR-related questions to clarify ownership, contribution agreements, and intended distribution rights.

This information is critical not only for managing rights and responsibilities but also for enabling software to be reused confidently by others. It also provides clarity for institutions and funders assessing compliance with policy frameworks.

5.2.6 Updated Document Templates

All updates to the Knowledge Model have been mirrored in the human-readable and machine-actionable document templates. The human-readable version provides improved formatting and contextualised headings to highlight contributor roles, reuse, and licensing. The machine-actionable exports (e.g. JSON, CodeMeta, and maSMP RDF) have been extended to include new fields and ensure compatibility with platforms such as Software Heritage and bio.tools.

These improvements further strengthen the SMP as a living, reusable document that can serve both internal project coordination and external reporting or archiving needs.

5.3 Cross-cutting Topics

Our work on implementing an architecture to support crediting of research software activities and contributions and on implementing SMPs is closely relevant and interconnecting as well as partially overlapping, since both efforts share common goals and face similar challenges. More specifically, SMPs provide a concrete mechanism for acknowledging software as a concrete research output, hence their adoption can drive the inclusion of software in research crediting practices, aligning with initiatives like CoARA that advocate for broader research contributions to be recognised. In addition, many of the components described in the architecture to support research software crediting can provide direct input to SMP platforms and vice versa. Finally, various standards and specifications that have been discussed in previous sections, such as those related to software PIDs, citation standards, and contribution roles are equally important for the implementation of crediting systems and SMPs hence the described opportunities and challenges relate to both efforts.

6. Conclusions

This report presents a comprehensive overview of the activities undertaken within ELIXIR-STEERS to support the recognition and sustainability of research software and workflows through credit mechanisms and Software Management Plans (SMPs). It reflects cross-Work Packages' collaboration and the integration of communities' feedback, resulting in notable progress towards inclusive research assessment practices.

The implementation of an inclusive research credit framework was a central focus, leading to the design of a detailed architectural blueprint, which comprises key components from publishing platforms, metadata services, and contributor tracking systems to gamification and academic profile tools. The report also emphasizes the value of specific standards (e.g. CodeMeta, CRediT, CITATION.cff) as well as the need for continued interoperability and refinement. The architecture of the blueprint is designed to be flexible and extensible, designed with the ability to connect with current infrastructure such as OpenAIRE Graph, ORCID, APICURON, and BIP! Scholar and to accommodate future community-driven extensions.

Parallel efforts to enhance SMPs, resulted in a significantly updated Software Management Planning Knowledge Model, informed by the principles of transparency, reusability, and structured credit. The updated version of the model supports FAIR and Open Science practices, enables export to machine-actionable formats, and integrates PIDs, including ORCID and ROR IDs, to strengthen attribution. This supports the documentation of both the development and reuse of research software, while also capturing contributor identities and their specific roles.

Throughout the ELIXIR-STEERS project, emphasis has been placed on producing practical results, ensuring technical reliability, and aligning with broader European and international efforts in responsible research assessment. This deliverable represents an important step in establishing inclusive and interoperable practices for crediting and planning within the research software lifecycle. It provides a blueprint, as a foundation for wider community adoption and future enhancements, supporting the full recognition of research software and workflows as essential elements of scholarly output.

7. Impact

In this section we outline the impact of the described activities and results in science, society and policy. We begin by examining the impact of our design for an inclusive research credit framework, followed by a discussion on the impact of our SMP concept.

7.1 Impact of Architecture for Inclusive Credit Framework

Our architecture is expected to have significant scientific impact. By proposing and refining a strategy to credit research artefacts beyond traditional publications (e.g., software, data, workflows, and training materials), ELIXIR-STEERS directly addresses a long-standing gap in the academic reward system. This promotes better practices in scientific software development and encourages sustainable research software engineering. In addition, it allows researchers to showcase a broader spectrum of their contributions, improving the visibility of roles often undervalued in science, such as software developers and data stewards, leading to a more accurate representation of individual and team contributions. Moreover, our study on existing infrastructures and how they can support a more inclusive and fair crediting system offers valuable insights to relevant stakeholders and paves the way for automated tracking and recognition of contributions across the research lifecycle. Finally, the collaboration with Tasks 3.2 ensures that best practices related to credit (e.g., citation standards, persistent identifiers, contributor roles) are embedded into research management tools, reinforcing responsible research data and software management.

Moving to the societal impact of our architecture, recognizing contributions beyond publications helps acknowledge the work of diverse roles and career paths, particularly those in support or technical positions (e.g., research software engineers, data curators). This contributes to a more inclusive and equitable research culture. Furthermore, by enhancing recognition mechanisms, the activities directly contribute to the professional development and motivation of researchers engaged in producing reusable research assets. This could also influence hiring, promotion, and funding decisions in more fair and transparent ways.

As regards the impact on policy, the development of a policy brief grounded in the technical and community-based work described in the current report ensures that we offer policy-level recommendations which are practical and actionable. It supports the wider push in European and global research policy towards Responsible Research Assessment (RRA). Additionally, the fact that our work contributed to efforts like EVERSE and CoARA's OI4RRA WG and vice versa helped to ensure alignment with emerging European policies and frameworks and foster synergies with relevant initiatives.

7.2 Impact of SMPs

Our concept and implementation of SMPs has direct and immediate scientific impact. First of all, SMPs promote the systematic documentation of research software development and maintenance practices and capture valuable information related to the dependencies and usage of software tools, as well as the exact contribution roles of researchers and research organisations. We guide researchers and developers from the earliest stages of their work, helping them make key decisions in a timely manner. This early guidance can lead to greater efficiency throughout the software lifecycle. These features are critical for ensuring that scientific results are reproducible and verifiable, while

supporting the broader recognition of software as a legitimate and citable research contribution, encouraging better practices and investment in software quality.

The societal impact is also immediate. By encouraging transparent planning, traceability, and accountability, SMPs contribute to more responsible and ethical software development and usage in research especially in domains that have societal relevance (e.g., health). Moreover, when research software is well-managed and appropriately documented, the general public and stakeholders (like policymakers) can place greater trust in the digital outputs and insights generated using the respective software tools.

Finally, regarding the impact on policy, SMPs contribute in operationalising FAIR for research software and further support policy mandates for Open Science. Moreover, since SMPs provide a concrete mechanism for acknowledging software as a concrete research output, their adoption can drive the inclusion of software in research assessment practices, aligning with initiatives like CoARA that advocate for broader research contributions to be recognised. The solution for software management planning is by design ready for iterative improvements, allowing it to evolve alongside ongoing developments in the field. This ensures alignment with emerging and ongoing efforts related to software quality metrics, sustainability, long-term archiving, and standards for reproducibility and transparency.

8. Next Steps

According to the project timeline, activities related to credit for research software contributions and to SMPs will continue until M30 (August 2026). Moving forward, efforts will concentrate on improving and extending the proof-of-concept implementations of the designed tools and standards, with the aim of demonstrating their value to project beneficiaries and external stakeholders, and gathering feedback for iterative improvement. All implementations are expected to evolve and be refined throughout the remaining duration of the relevant tasks, building on both the opportunities and gaps identified in this report and any future feedback received. In parallel, particular attention will be given to enhancing and expanding the documentation that supports these implementations, to ensure clarity and usability. Finally, the ongoing work to translate technical developments related to credit and recognition of research software activities and contributions into policy recommendations, will continue through to the publication of the policy brief that is currently under development.

9. Deviation from Description of Action

Not applicable.

References

Batut, B., Ben-Avraham, D., Capella-Gutierrez, S., Carazo, J. M., Fernandez, J. M., Golobardes Vilarasau, A., Mehdiabadi, M., Piovesan, D., Redondo, A., Sanchez de Lara, L., Schwämmle, V., Tosatto, S., Yahalomi, D., & Zierep, P. (2025). ELIXIR-STEERS M3.3 Use cases for benchmarking workflows identified. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15363545>

Bouhraoua, A., Vergoulis, T., Makaronidou, M., Quaglia, F., & Tosatto, S. (2024). ELIXIR-STEERS Report M3.1 Strategy for inclusion of credit for research assets decided. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14017751>

Eva Martín del Pico, Josep Lluís Gelpí, Salvador Capella-Gutierrez, FAIRsoft—a practical implementation of FAIR principles for research software, *Bioinformatics*, Volume 40, Issue 8, August (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btae464>

Katz, D. S., Bouquin, D., Hong, N. P. C., Hausman, J., Jones, C., Chivvis, D., ... & Zhang, Q. (2019). Software citation implementation challenges. arXiv preprint arXiv:1905.08674.

Matthew Feickert, Daniel S. Katz, Mark S. Neubauer, Elizabeth Sexton-Kennedy and Graeme A. Stewart. (2024). Software Citation in HEP: Current State and Recommendations for the Future 08017. <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/202429508017>

Smith AM, Katz DS, Niemeyer KE, FORCE11 Software Citation Working Group. (2016). Software citation principles. PeerJ Computer Science, <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.86>

Suchánek, M., Slifka, J., Ioannidis, V., Ibberson, M., Coppens, F., Capella-Gutierrez, S., Portell-Silva, L., Nyberg, M., & Schwämmle, V. (2025). ELIXIR-STEERS M3.2 Report: First version of Software Management Plan interface implemented in Data Stewardship Wizard. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14810275>

Appendix A: List of Abbreviations

API: Application Programming Interface

DSW: Data Stewardship Wizard

DMP: Data Management Plan

EOSC: European Open Science Cloud

FAIR: Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (principles for data stewardship)

PID: Persistent Identifier

RRA: Responsible Research Assessment

SKG: Scientific Knowledge Graph

SMP: Software Management Plan

WG: Working Group

WP: Work Package

